

Incidence of Hypothyroidism in Patients suffering from β Thalassemia Major.

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Abstract:

Objective: The main aim of this study was to find the incidence of hypothyroidism in patients who were suffering from β thalassemia major.

Place and Duration of Study: This study was carried out in a duration of 8 months from June 2019 to January 2020 in Pediatrics department Mayo hospital Lahore.

Study Design: It is a cross sectional type of study.

Sampling Technique: Non-probability consecutive sampling technique

Materials and Methods: A total of 75 cases of patients suffering from β thalassemia major were selected for this study. Age limit was between 5 to 15 years. Patients from both genders were selected randomly. 3ml blood sample was taken and sent to a reliable laboratory for assessing the levels of T4 and TSH. ELISA kit was used to assess the levels of T4 and TSH. This data was analyzed using SPSS version 20 to assess the percentage and frequency of Hypothyroidism. Informed consent was taken from relatives of the patients and ethical approval was taken from the hospital committee.

Inclusion criteria:

- * Confirmed cases β Thalassemia major.
- * Between the age of 5 to 15 years of either gender.
- * Exclusion criteria:
- * Patients with acute disease
- * Patients of thalassemia minor and intermedia

Results: Hypothyroidism was seen in children with the mean age of 10.48 ± 2.6 years. A total of 22 (29.3%) patients were suffering from hypothyroidism. Among these 8 (30.8%) were female patients and 14 (28.6%) were male patients.

Conclusion: Even in the absence of signs and symptoms, children with β thalassemia major can also suffer from hypothyroidism. Thus it is absolutely necessary to screen the children with beta thalassemia major regularly for hypothyroidism to make early diagnosis and to provide rapid treatment.

Keywords: Hypothyroidism, T4, TSH, β thalassemia major.

Introduction: β thalassemia is an autosomal recessive disorder in which there is abnormal production of hemoglobin β chain. There are three types β thalassemia major, intermedia and minor. In patients who are suffering from major form and becomes symptomatic, there is severe anemia

during the second half of first year of life and massive blood transfusions are required. Among the monogenic disorders, it is most common all over the world. Around 9000 children suffer from β thalassemia major each year in Pakistan. The approximated carrier rate is 5-7%.

There are two treatment modalities stem cell transplantation and regular blood transfusion. There are multiple complications associated with repeated excessive blood transfusions. One of the most common is excessive iron deposition in different organs of the body leading to early death. Survival rate has been improved with the use of iron chelators but at the cost of increased frequency of endocrine complications including hypogonadism, cardiomyopathy, diabetes mellitus, hypothyroidism and hypoparathyroidism in long term survivors.

Sub-clinical, primary and central type of hypothyroidism has been seen in patients suffering from β thalassemia major and among these most commonly seen is subclinical type. Signs and symptoms of hypothyroidism include cold intolerance, constipation, poor school performance, weight gain and lethargy. Incidence of hypothyroidism in patients with β thalassemia major varies from 7-78%. A study was carried out in Children hospital Lahore, Hematology department which included 70 patients of beta thalassemia major in which hypothyroidism was seen in 25.7% of the patients.

Aim of our study was to find the incidence of hypothyroidism in patients with major type of beta thalassemia as the results of previous studies varies considerably. It may put an emphasis on the early diagnosis and prompt management of complications related to the endocrine system and may result in decreased mortality.

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Table 1: Gender distribution (n=75)

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	49	65.5
Female	26	34.7
Total	75	100.0

Table 2: Age distribution (n=75)

Age Distribution	Frequency	Percent
5-10 years	35	46.7
11-15 years	40	53.3
Total	75	100.0

Table 3: Mean TSH and T4 levels (n=75)

TSH/T4	Mean	Std. Deviation
TSH	4.4400	1.7339
T4	9.2267	1.4665

Table 4: Frequency of hypothyroidism frequency:

Hypothyroidism	Frequency	Percent
Yes	22	29.3
No	53	70.7
Total	75	100.0

Discussion: For last several decades, repeated blood transfusions has increased life expectancy in

patients with beta thalassemia major. Use of iron chelators have decreased complications but this

therapy is expensive, not easily accessible and difficult to administer and poor compliance is seen leading to excessive iron in the body.

Early diagnosis and treatment of endocrine abnormalities related with excessive repeated blood transfusion is important as it can decrease mortality. Most important among endocrinal abnormalities is hypothyroidism because it can lead to growth abnormalities which is very common in patients with beta thalassemia major. According to our study, all the patients had normal levels of T4 levels except one while high levels of TSH was seen in 22 patients and normal in 53 patients. Among 75 total tested patients 22 were suffering from hypothyroidism. The results of our study are in accordance with the study of Malik et al in which he showed incidence of hypothyroidism to be 25.7% in patients with beta thalassemia major. The slight variation in our study can be explained by the difference in treatment protocols.

Thyroid gland dysfunction can be caused by the excessive deposition of iron in thyroid gland. One of the major concerns in beta thalassemia major patients is iron overload and an important factor for management.

Signs and symptoms of iron overload usually appears in 2nd decade of life but multiple liver biopsies done at an early stage of life shows that toxic effects of iron deposition begins early. Mechanism by which tissue damage occurs due to iron overload is not fully understood yet but is has

been attributed to the lipid peroxidation and formation of free radicals which damage lysosomal, mitochondrial and sarcolemmal membranes. Tissue damage occurring in thyroid gland leads to hypothyroidism.

Thyroid dysfunction was seen most commonly in older children showing a correlation between hypothyroidism and old age in patients with beta thalassemia major. 10.48 was the mean age of patients in our study. It was also seen that there is a relation between age and increased ferritin levels. This is because of the reason that more blood has been transfused to the elder children leading to iron overload. Subclinical hypothyroidism was seen in 22 patients of our study with the age greater than 11 years and they were not taking regular chelation therapy. No significant correlation was seen between gender and hypothyroidism.

Further studies are needed to find the correlation between thyroid dysfunction and iron overload in patients with beta thalassemia major. In excessively overloaded patients serum ferritin level is a poor indicator there is a chance of underestimation of role of iron in thyroid dysfunction.

Conclusion: Even in the absence of signs and symptoms, children with β thalassemia major can also suffer from hypothyroidism. Thus it is absolutely necessary to screen the children with beta thalassemia major regularly for hypothyroidism to make early diagnosis and to provide rapid treatment.

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